

BASAL CROCODYLOMORPHA

†*Junggarsuchus sloani*

BASAL CROCODYLIFORMES

†*Eopneumatosuchus colberti*

†*Protosuchus haughtoni*

THALATTOSUCHIA

†*Cricosaurus araucanensis*

†*Cricosaurus schroederi*

†*Macrospodylus bollensis*

†*Metriorhynchus* cf. '*M.*' *brachyrhynchus*

†*Pelagosaurus typus*

†*Plagiophthalmosuchus* cf. *P. gracilirostris*

TETHYSUCHIA

†*Rhabdognathus aslerensis*

EUSUCHIA

Alligator mississippiensis (neonate)

Alligator mississippiensis

Alligator mississippiensis

Caiman crocodilus

Crocodylus acutus

Crocodylus intermedius

Crocodylus johnstoni

Crocodylus moreletii

Crocodylus porosus (juvenile)

Crocodylus rhombifer

Gavialis gangeticus

Gavialis gangeticus

†*Gryposuchus neogaeus*

†*Gunggamarandu maunala*

Mecistops cataphractus

†*Mourasuchus arendsi*

Osteolaemus tetraspis

Tomistoma schlegelii

Tomistoma schlegelii

†*Trilophosuchus rackhami*